

High Volume Fly Ash Green Concrete mixed with Glass Fibre for Ordinary Civil Engineering Purposes

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Abstract

Concrete is the most common material used in the construction of civil engineering structures and the global demand for concrete is significantly increased due to infrastructure growth worldwide. The production of Portland cement which is the main ingredient of concrete is not only costly but energy intensive. It consumes approximately 7.0 GJ (Gigajoule) of energy per ton of cement production and also cement production process results in the emission of large amount of CO₂, a greenhouse gas. To overcome these problems, there is a need to find some replacement to some extent. By the use of green concrete, it is possible to reduce the CO₂ emission in atmosphere towards eco-friendly construction technique. Fly ash, a much potential industrial waste product that replaces cement in the concrete, is discussed in depth in this particular paper. In this study, the potential use of siliceous/class F fly ash from power plant Kolaghat as a partial replacement of cement is studied. Concrete mix M20 is designed with water-cement ratio 0.42 by adding 50% of fly ash (Siliceous/Class-F) as a partial replacement of cement, without using any other chemical admixture. Six concrete cubes of size 150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm were cast and tested for compressive strength at 28 days, 56 days and 90 days curing for all mixes. The analysis of results shows the promising values with respect to compressive strength as well as workability. Thus, green concrete may be used as a partial replacement of cement by means of fly ash as it is cheaper, because it uses waste products, saving energy consumption in the production. The result also shows that at initial stages strength gain is less for fly ash mixed green concrete and the strength is becoming higher at later ages. To overcome this delayed curing and lower initial values of compressive strength glass fibres are mixed with this high volume fly ash concrete. So the required compressive strength value is achieved within the curing time. Also the crack widths become lesser. Above all, glass fibre mixed high volume fly ash green concrete has greater strength and durability than the normal concrete using for ordinary civil engineering construction purposes.

Keywords: Concrete, Green technology, High volume fly ash, Eco-Friendly construction material, Glass fibre, Timely curing, More durability.

Introduction

Green concrete is a concept of using eco-friendly materials in concrete, to make the system more sustainable. It can be defined as the concrete with material as a partial or complete replacement for cement or fine or coarse aggregates. The substitution material can be of waste or residual product in the manufacturing process. The substituted materials could be a waste material that remains unused, that may be harmful (material that contains radioactive elements). There are many industrial waste products that have the potential to replace cement in concrete, however, fly ash is the industrial waste

material that is discussed in depth in this paper. By the use of green concrete, it is possible to reduce the CO₂ emission in atmosphere towards eco-friendly construction technique. Fly ash produced from the burning of pulverized coal in a coal-fired boiler is a fine-grained, powdery particulate material that is carried off in the flue gas and usually collected from the flue gas by means of electrostatic precipitators or mechanical collection devices such as cyclones. Fly ash is the notorious waste product of coal-based electricity generating thermal power plants, known for its ill effects on agricultural land, surface and sub-surface water pollution, soil and air pollution and diseases to mankind like cancer. Fly ash is also known as a good pozzolanic material and has been used to increase the ultimate compressive strength and workability of fresh concrete. This paper summarizes the various efforts underway to improve the environmental friendliness of concrete by using HVFA as the partial replacement of cement without using any chemical admixture. High volume fly ash constitutes about 50% fly ash, lower water content, low cement content and a low water-cement ratio. Use of HVFA in concrete is gaining significance and is considered as a sustainable option for many concrete constructions. HVFA concrete has lower strength at early ages but at a later age, HVFA concrete shows a continuous increase in strength properties. To overcome this delayed curing and lower initial values of compressive strength glass fibre is mixed with this high volume fly ash concrete. Significantly both the crack width and drying shrinkage are also reduced and thus contribute to the long-term durability of concrete. HVFA GFRC concrete exhibits comparable costs, increased strengths and enhanced durability.

Related Work

Previous studies reveal that the addition of fly ash mixed green concrete resulted in great profits such as reducing in heat of hydration, minimization of inherent alkali-aggregate reaction, significant reduction of steel corrosion, improvement in durability of concrete, decrease in cost etc. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6,7]. In extension, it enhances the environment by contributing towards the reduction of greenhouse gases. The objective of this investigation is to study the effect of high volume of fly ash in the fresh and hardened properties of concrete.

Fly ash as cementitious material

Fly ash is a very fine powder and tends to travel far in the air. When not properly disposed of, it is known to pollute air and water and causes respiratory problems when inhaled. When it settles on leaves and crops in fields around the power plant, it lowers the yield. When pulverized coal is burnt to generate heat, the residue contains 80% fly ash and 20% bottom ash. Fly ash produced in Indian power stations are light to mid-grey in color and have the appearance of cement powder. Use of fly ash concrete in place of PCC will not only enable substantial savings in the consumption of cement and energy but also provide economy. The use of fly ash has a number of advantages. It is theoretically possible to replace 100% of Portland cement by fly ash, but replacement levels above 80% generally require a chemical activator. Studies have found that the optimum replacement level is around 30%. Moreover, fly ash can improve certain properties of concrete, such as durability. Because it generates less heat of hydration, it is particularly well suited for mass concrete applications. The use of fly ash in concrete in optimum proportion has many technical benefits and improves concrete performance in both fresh and hardened state. Fly ash used in concrete improves the workability of

plastic concrete and the strength and durability of hardened concrete. Generally, fly ash benefits concrete by reducing the mixing water requirement and improving the paste flow behavior.

Benefits of using high volume fly ash in concrete

Advantages of using fly ash in concrete include the followings:

- ✓ High volume fly ash in the concrete mix efficiently replaces Portland cement that in turn can aid in making big savings in concrete material prices.
- ✓ It is also an environment-friendly solution, which meets the performance specifications. It can also contribute to LEED points.
- ✓ It improves the strength over time and thus, it offers greater strength to the structure.
- ✓ Increased density and also the long-term strengthening the action of flash that ties up with free lime and thus, results in lower bleed channels and also decreases the permeability.
- ✓ The reduced permeability of concrete by using fly ash also aids to keep aggressive composites on the surface where the damaging action is reduced. It is also highly resistant to attack by mild acid, water and sulphate.
- ✓ It effectively combines with alkalis from cement, which thereby prevents the destructive expansion.
- ✓ It is also helpful in reducing the heat of hydration.
- ✓ The pozzolanic reaction in between lime and fly ash will significantly generate less heat and thus, prevents thermal cracking.
- ✓ It chemically and effectively binds salts and free lime, which can create efflorescence. The lower permeability of fly ash concrete can efficiently reduce the effects of efflorescence.
- ✓ HVFA concrete is more sustainable concrete compared to conventional concrete as it reduces the usage of cement and also reduces environmental pollution.
- ✓ HVFA concrete performs well at a later stage than at an early age.
- ✓ Low water-cement ratio and adequate curing are essential for strength gain.
- ✓ The long-term permeability of HVFAC is very low.
- ✓ HVFA concrete is effective in controlling temperature effects in mass concrete applications.
- ✓ HVFA concrete can be safely used in Concrete Pavements and other ordinary civil engineering purposes for economic and ecological benefits.
- ✓ Fly ash contents of up to 50% may be suitable for most elements provided the early-age strength requirements of the project can be met and provided that adequate moist-curing can be ensured.

Experimental Program

In this study, the potential use of siliceous fly ash from power plant Kolaghat as a partial replacement of cement is studied. The experimental program is designed to investigate the influence of various parameters on the concrete compressive strength and it is executed in two phases.

Phase I: High Volume Fly Ash mixed M20 grade Concrete

High volume fly ash mixed (50 % as the partial replacement of cement) green concrete is made using siliceous fly ash. For this phase I, concrete mix M20 is designed with water-cement ratio 0.42 by adding 50% of fly ash (Siliceous/Class-F) as a partial replacement of cement, without using any

chemical admixture. Six concrete cubes of size 150 mm x 150mm x 150 mm are cast and tested for compressive strength at 28 days, 56 days and 90 days curing for all mixes.

Materials used

1. *Cement*: In the present study, 43 grade Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) with a specific gravity of 3.12 is used throughout the investigation. The cement satisfies the requirement of IS-8112.

2. *Fine aggregate*: The natural river sand available in the local market which passes through 4.75 mm IS sieve and conforming to zone I of IS 383 is used. Specific gravity and fineness modulus of sand used are 2.62 and 2.73 respectively.

3. *Coarse aggregate*: The crushed coarse aggregate of 20 mm maximum size as well as 12 mm size are obtained from the local crushing plant, is used in the present study. The specific gravity of the coarse aggregate used is 2.65.

4. *Water*: Water is an important ingredient of concrete as it actively participated in a chemical reaction with cement, clean potable water which is available on our college campus is used.

5. *Fly ash*: In the present investigation work, siliceous fly ash used is obtained from Kolaghat power station in India with a specific gravity of 2.03 as per IS:1727. Fly ash meeting specifications of IS: 3812 & IS: 456.

Mix proportioning

In this phase, M20 grade mix is designed based on the guidelines given by IS 10262-2009. Mix design is done using water-cement ratio 0.42.

Stipulation for proportioning:

a. Grade design	:	M20
b. Type of cement	:	OPC 43 grade
c. Types of mineral admixture	:	Fly ash
d. Maximum nominal size of aggregate	:	20 mm
e. Minimum cement content	:	300 kg/m ³
f. Maximum water cement ratio	:	0.45
g. Workability	:	25 - 50 mm (slump)
h. Exposure condition	:	Mild (for rcc)
i. Degree of supervision	:	Good
j. Type of aggregate	:	Crushed angular aggregate
k. Chemical admixture type	:	Nil

Test data for materials:

a. Cement used	:	OPC 43 grade
b. Specific gravity of cement	:	3.12
c. Fly ash	:	Conforming to IS: 3812

d.	Specific gravity of fly ash	:	2.03
e.	Chemical admixture	:	Nil
f.	Specific gravity of		
	1. Coarse aggregate	:	2.65
	2. Fine aggregate	:	2.62
g.	Water absorption		
	1. Coarse aggregate	:	0.82 %
	2. Fine aggregate	:	0.80 %
h.	Free (surface) moisture		
	1. Coarse aggregate	:	Nil (absorbed moisture nil)
	2. Fine aggregate	:	Nil
i.	Sieve analysis		
	1. Coarse aggregate	:	Conforming to table 2 IS:383
	2. Fine aggregate	:	Zone 1 of table 4 IS: 383

Target Strength for mix proportioning:

$$f'_{ck} = f_{ck} + 1.65 s$$

Where, f'_{ck} = target average compressive strength at 28 days,
 f_{ck} = characteristics compressive strength at 28 days, and
 s = standard deviation = 5 N/mm²

Therefore, target strength (f'_{ck}) = 20 + 1.65 x 5 = 28.25 N/mm²

Selection of water-cement ratio:

From Table 5 of IS 456, maximum water-cement ratio = 0.55.

Based on experience, adopt water-cement ratio as 0.42.

0.42 < 0.55, hence O.K.

Selection of water content:

Maximum water content for 20 mm aggregate = 186 liters (for 25 to 50 mm slump range).

Calculation of cement and fly ash content:

Water-cement ratio = 0.42

Cementations material (cement+ fly ash) content = 186/0.42 = 442.857 kg/m³

From table 5 of IS 456, minimum cement content for 'severe' exposure conditions = 320 kg/m³

442.857 kg/m³ > 320 kg/m³, hence O.K.

Now, to proportion a mix containing fly ash the following steps are suggested:

- Decide the percentage fly ash to be used based on project requirement and quality of materials
- In certain situation increase in cementations material content may be warranted. The decision on increase in cementations material content and its percentage may be based on experience and trial.

Note: This example is with an increase of 10 % cementations material content.

Cementations material content = 442.857 x 1.10 = 487.142 kg/m³

Water content = 186 kg/m³

So, water-cement ratio = 186/487.142 = 0.381

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Fly ash @ 50\% of total cementations material content} &= 487.142 \times 0.50 = 243.571 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ \text{Cement (OPC)} &= 487.142 - 243.571 = 243.571 \text{ kg/m}^3\end{aligned}$$

Proportion of volume of coarse aggregate and fine aggregate content:

From Table 3, volume of coarse aggregate corresponding to 20 mm size aggregate and fine aggregate for water-cement ratio of 0.50-0.60. In the present case water-cement ratio is 0.42. Therefore, volume of coarse aggregate is required to be increased to decrease the fine aggregate content. As the water-cement ratio is lower by 0.08, the proportion of volume of coarse aggregate is increased by 0.016 (at the rate of ± 0.01 for every ± 0.05 change in water-cement ratio). Therefore, corrected proportion of volume of coarse aggregate for the water-cement ratio of 0.42 is 0.616.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Therefore, volume of coarse aggregate} &= 0.616 \\ \text{Volume of fine aggregate} &= 1 - 0.616 = 0.384\end{aligned}$$

Mix calculations per unit volume of concrete:

- a. Volume of concrete = 1 m³
- b. Volume of cement = Mass of cement / (1000 x specific gravity of cement)
= 243.571 / (3.12 x 1000) = 0.078 m³
- c. Volume of fly ash = Mass of fly ash / (1000 x specific gravity of fly ash)
= 243.571 / (2.03 x 1000) = 0.119 m³
- d. Volume of water = Mass of water / (1000 x specific gravity of water)
= 186 / (1000 x 1) = 0.186 m³
- e. Volume of all in aggregate = [a - (b + c + d)]
= [1 - (0.078 + 0.119 + 0.186)]
= 0.617 m³
- f. Mass of coarse aggregate = e X volume of coarse aggregate X specific gravity of coarse aggregate X 1000
= 0.617 X 0.616 X 2.65 X 1000 = 1007.19 kg
- g. Mass of fine aggregate = e X volume of fine aggregate X specific gravity of fine aggregate X 1000
= 0.617 X 0.384 X 2.62 X 1000 = 620.75 kg

Mix proportions:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Cement} &= 243.571 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ \text{Fly ash} &= 243.571 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ \text{Water} &= 186 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ \text{Fine aggregate} &= 620.75 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ \text{Coarse aggregate} &= 1007.19 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ \text{Water cement ratio} &= 0.381\end{aligned}$$

So the final ratio is **0.50:0.50:1.274:2.06**

Casting: Standard cast iron moulds of Cube of dimensions 150mm x 150mm x 150mm are used to cast the specimens for compression test. The side plates of the mould were sufficiently stiff to

eliminate spreading and warping. Before the concrete was placed in the mould, all the joints were checked thoroughly for any leakage. A thin film of grease was applied to cover the joints between the halves of the mould at the bottom surface of the mould and its base plate in order to ensure that no water escapes.

Curing: After casting, the specimens are stored in the laboratory at room temperature for 24 hours. After these periods the specimens are removed from the moulds and immediately submerged in clean, fresh water of curing tank and specimens are cured for 28, 56 and 90 days in the present investigation work.

Strength: Of the various strengths of concrete, the determination of compression has received a large amount of attention because the concrete is primarily meant to withstand compressive stresses. Generally, cubes are used to determine the compressive strength. In the present investigation, the size of concrete moulds 150 x 150 x 150 mm are used. In the compressive test, the cube while cleaned to wipe of the surface water, is placed with the cast faces in contact with the planes of the testing machine, i.e. the position of the cube then tested is at right angles to that as cast. The specimens are removed from the moulds and submerged in clean fresh water until just prior to testing. The temperature of water in which the cubes are submerged is maintained at 27^o C +/- 2^o C and 90% relative humidity for 24 hours. The specimens are cured for 28, 56, and 90 days.

Tests of concrete cubes with fly ash: Compressive strength tests are carried out on cubes of 150 mm size using a compression testing machine of 2000 KN capacity as per IS 516:1959. The casted cubes are to be tested for 28 days, 56 days, and 90 days.

Result and Discussion:

The 28, 56 and 90 days' compressive strength tests are carried out and the results are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Compressive test results of Phase-I mixes at various stages of curing (50% Fly ash)

Age of testing (Days)	Compressive strength of concrete cubes in N/mm ²
28	16
56	22
90	27

The analysis of result shows the promising values with respect to compressive strength as well as workability. The most important benefit is reduced permeability to water and aggressive chemicals. Properly cured concrete made with fly ash creates a denser product because the size of the pores is reduced. This increases strength and reduces permeability. The result also shows that at initial stages strength gain is less for HVFA mixed green concrete and the strength is higher at later ages. Over and above all green concrete has greater strength and durability than the normal concrete.

Limitations of HVFA mixed concrete:

Also there are some limitations of using fly ash that should be considered. The quality of fly ash to be utilized is very vital. Poor quality often has a negative impact on the concrete. The poor quality can increase the permeability and thus damaging the building. Some fly ash, those are produced in power plant is usually compatible with concrete, while some other needs to be beneficiated and few other types cannot actually be improved for use in concrete. Thus it is very much vital to use only high-

quality fly ash to prevent negative effects on the structure. Some of the shortcomings of HVFA concrete are:

- Extended setting times.
- Slow development of strength.
- Low early age strength.
- Delay in Construction.
- Difficult to use in cold weather concreting.
- Low resistance to deicer-salt scaling and carbonation.

Phase II: Glass Fibre Reinforced High Volume Fly Ash Concrete

With the addition of Glass Fibre into the previous mix design procedure (water : cement ratio = 0.40 here) the 7 days, 28 days, 56 days and 90 days compressive strengths are studied and the values are shown in the tabular form in Table 2 for three specimens in each category. The compressive strength of concrete with maximum nominal size of aggregates 20mm is studied. The 7 days, 28 days, 56 days and 90 days compressive strengths are also plotted in Figure 1 by taking the average of these three values.

Mix proportions used here

- Cement = 228 kg/m³
- Fly ash = 228 kg/m³
- Water = 186 kg/m³
- Fine aggregate = 682 kg/m³
- Coarse aggregate = 1066 kg/m³
- Water cement ratio = 0.40
- So the final ratio is **0.50 : 0.50 : 1.496 : 2.337**
- Glass fibre = 2.74 kg/m³**

Table 2: Compressive Strength

Sr. No.	Cube Specification	Grade of concrete (f _{ck} = 20 N/mm ²)	Age of specimen in days	Dimension of specimen in cm	Cross sectional area of specimen in cm ²	Actual crushing load in Kg	Comp. strength in Kg/cm ²	Average comp. strength in Kg/cm ²	Specified limit for days	
									7days	28days
1	1	M20	7	15×15×15	225	31500	140.00	142.22		
2	2	M20	7	15×15×15	225	32500	144.44		M20	M20
3	3	M20	7	15×15×15	225	32000	142.22		135	200
4	1	M20	28	15×15×15	225	46500	206.67	208.89		
5	2	M20	28	15×15×15	225	47500	211.11			
6	3	M20	28	15×15×15	225	47000	208.89			
7	1	M20	56	15×15×15	225	50000	222.22	223.70		
8	2	M20	56	15×15×15	225	51000	226.67			
9	3	M20	56	15×15×15	225	50000	222.22			
10	1	M20	90	15×15×15	225	53500	237.78	237.04		
11	2	M20	90	15×15×15	225	53500	237.78			
12	3	M20	90	15×15×15	225	53000	235.56			

Figure 1: Effect of Glass Fibre on Compressive Strength of Concrete

Flexural Strength

Table 3 Flexural Strength

Laboratory Test Certificate

- Test done for** : Mr. Somsubhra De, M-Tech Student (Structural Engg.), Techno India, Salt Lake, Sector - V, Kolkata.
- Letter Memo No.** : Nil Dated:- 18/01/2019
- Sample Size** : 1) 500mm X 100mm X 100mm
2) 700mm X 150mm X 150mm
- Grade of Concrete** : M20
- Type of Test** : Flexural Strength of Concrete Beam (as per IS: 516)

Test Results:-

Sample Marked	Date of Casting	Date of Testing	Strength (N/mm ²)
Sample - 1 (Size - 500mm X 100mm X 100mm)	19/09/2018	22/01/2019	4.12
Sample - 2 (Size - 500mm X 100mm X 100mm)			4.36
Sample - 3 (Size - 700mm X 150mm X 150mm)			4.82

Note:- 1. Tests were conducted in the laboratory as per relevant code on the samples as sent by the party.

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We recommend the average value of 4.12 and 4.36 i.e. $(4.12 + 4.36) / 2 = 4.24 \text{ N/mm}^2 = 42.4 \text{ kg/cm}^2$ tensile strength (refer above Table 3). The crack width is also less than normal concrete beam.

Conclusions

HVFA mixed green concrete has manifold advantages over the conventional concrete. Since it uses the recycled aggregates and materials, it reduces the extra load in landfills and mitigates the wastage of aggregates. Thus, the net CO₂ emissions are reduced. Since a huge quantity of cement is used in concrete in mass concrete construction and the cost of fly ash is negligible as compared to that of the cement, the use of HVFA concrete brings about a substantial saving in cement consumption and overall construction cost. HVFA mixed green concrete may be used in general RCC structures including road pavements, dam construction etc. without any risk of steel corrosion. The fly ash is an industrial waste and great hazard for our environment. The designers of concrete structures, therefore, must incorporate the use of fly ash in their structural concrete. It reduces the consumption of cement

overall and has better workability, greater strength and durability than normal concrete. Only drawback of this concept is the delay in initial strength gain and thus the curing time is extended upto 90 days instead of 28 days. This problem can be overcome by the use of glass fibre in the concrete mix design. Then the strength gain will be same as normal concrete characteristic strength gain timings. Also the cracks and shrinkage effects will be less and the HVFA GFRC concrete will be more durable for longer period of time. By using this concept we can save environment and can give this environment to our next generation.

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